

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' BASIC COMPETENCES THROUGH WORKING ON TEXT IN MOTHER LANGUAGE CLASSES

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ANNOTATION

Working on the text in the native language classes develops students' reading comprehension, listening comprehension, oral and written literacy, broad observation, and creative thinking. Also, in the article, examples of assignments on the text are given, and special attention is paid to reading, listening and understanding of the text assignments. Didactic tasks were given to improve the methodology of working on the text based on the tasks corresponding to the texts given on the basis of the 4th grade textbook.

Key words: text, creativity, scientific text, poetic text. reading comprehension, listening comprehension

INTRODUCTION

In forming the knowledge of the youth of Uzbekistan in accordance with the requirements of international standards, taking a model from the world's advanced educational systems, quickly and easily mastering and applying effective methods is an important issue. Language is the main criterion that shows ideology, spiritual maturity, and intellectual potential. Also, the basis and basis for learning foreign languages is definitely our mother tongue. Learning a language in the world community requires 4 basic skills: reading, listening comprehension, oral and written communication literacy. Today, in mother tongue classes, while working on the largest language unit - texts, which differ from each other in terms of their structure and content, it is necessary to strengthen various knowledge, skills and abilities of students, to develop their worldview, to observe and It is also important to develop analytical approaches. While working on the text, the reader faces various complications and difficulties, and finding ways to get out of a problematic situation and find solutions is an interesting and observational process that requires thoughtful work. It is natural that working on the text is not limited to what is given in the textbook, but it is also interesting and enjoyable for the students to work on scientific and fiction literature, selected texts from the periodical press, and

audio-video tapes. If we pay attention, there are many different ways of working on the text in mother tongue education. We will consider some of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

I. The method of working with grammatical tasks on the text (traditional practice)

1. Separating words from the given text related to the topic to be studied, grouping them by word groups, separating, defining, comparing, finding or grouping word-forming, modifying and form-forming adverbs .
2. Creating compound sentences from simple sentences in the text and simplifying compound sentences on the contrary.
3. Syntactic analysis of separated simple and compound sentences.
4. Telling the content of poetic works in prose.
5. Separation of compound sentences in the text, identification of types.
5. Morphological or syntactic analysis of the given sentence v.h.

II. Method of approach to the problem given in the text based on creative, logical observations (updated practice)

1. To replace the highlighted words in the text with phrases and figurative expressions, to determine and interpret their dictionary meaning.
2. Finding words with the same, similar, similar and opposite meanings to the separated words and interpreting their dictionary meaning;
3. Transforming a text in a scientific style into a text in an artistic style;
4. Change the form of the text while keeping the content;
5. Finding and understanding the information given in the text (scanning the text): searching for specific information (number, name, etc.) in the text.

6. Creating an artistic (scientific, pictorial poetic) text based on a given electronic image (picture, drawing, chart) v.h. Below we will try to prove our thoughts by working on the poetic text. The following are important in the analysis of poetic texts:

1. Preparing to read and understand a poetic text. Before reading and analyzing the poetic text, methodical work is carried out to prepare the students to understand the meaning of the poem and encourage them to think. It is advisable to use wise words, proverbs, riddles, stories, legends or narratives related to the subject of the poem.

For example, we can see this process in the example of the analysis of the text "My dream" given in the 4th grade textbook. First of all, the following questions are directed to the attention of the readers, the theme expressed in the poem, the proposed idea?

My dream

I want to become a doctor in the future. I was interested in becoming a doctor when I was a child. Because my mother is a doctor. I envy them. I need to be good at all subjects to realize my dream. In particular, I am trying to study the mother tongue, English, and biology in depth.

What professions do you know?

What qualities should a doctor have?

What do you mean by good deeds?

2. Expressive reading of the text. This is a very important process, requiring the student to concentrate.

3. After listening to the text, the students' understanding of the text will be determined based on the following tasks.

Task 1. To find and understand the information given in the text ("scanning" the text): to search for concretely expressed information (number, name, etc.) in the text. it was determined to what extent the students understood the meaning of words and phrases based on the text. Question: Match the synonyms and the correct words

1. doctor a) profession;
2. science b) mother tongue, English
3. interest c) person's desire;

Task 2: Understanding the function of the syntactic elements used in the text (conjunctions, pronouns, modal words, etc.) in the text. Because my mother is a doctor. I need to be good at all subjects to realize my dream. In particular, I am trying to study the mother tongue, English, and biology in depth.

Question: Determine the correct sentences about the given passage (2 answers are correct).

- A. There is a simple participle sentence.
- B. The functional connective served to connect the combined fillers.
- C. In the passage, the artificial person noun is used as an imperative.
- D. Relative forms of the verb are used without a sign.
- E. Sentences have units for all 3 types of auxiliary words.

Task 3: To be able to paraphrase the information expressed in one or more sentences in the text. Question: Identify proverbs that match the meaning of the poem.

- A. Be a shepherd in your country until you become a king in another country.
- B. There is no job for an ignorant person
- There is no soup for a person without knowledge

C. The sentence is not cooked with -.

D. Stretch your arms

Task 4. Read the information, determine "correct" and "incorrect" information.

Question. The text begins with a call to compatriots.

A. That's right

B. Incorrect

Question. The text discusses the medical profession.

A. True B. False

Task 6. Choose the correct sentence according to the content of the text

7. For sprouts and flowers to flourish...

A. Everyone should have a profession

B. It is necessary to plant a flower garden near the garden.

C. Getting the profession of your dreams brings happiness.

D. Give water and call this place Mehr.

II. Working on a scientific text

At first, soups were prepared from animals that people hunted... with meat and bones... This kind of food was invented thousands of years ago. Ancient Greece... soup was considered the fastest "fast food". Streets... anyone could have a plate of soup made with lentils, peas and similar cereals... and drink it. The word "soup" (soup) appeared in the Middle Ages. This word comes from the ancient word "sop". he... the pot in which the meat was boiled... the water left at the bottom... they ate. Uzbekistan... winter... - hot, summer... - cold soups are old... consumed.

Tasks on the text

Assignment 1 Question 1. Find and fill in the words that need to be added from the text?

Animal..., We..., Eramiz..., Greece..., Streets..., Ages..., Sozi..., Chik..., u..., dish..., water..., Uzbekison..., Winter..., Ancient... .

Task 2. Question 1. Determine whether the words in the first column separated from the text can have the correct explanation of these words from the second column. 1) soup 2) soup 3) soup 4) fast food

3 - task. Question 2. Ancient Greece... soup was considered the fastest "fast-food" dish.. Determine the correct sentences about the noun phrase used in the given sentence (2 correct answers)

A. The noun in the exit agreement is subordinate to the passive verb.

B. There is an artificial noun in the form of "base + form builder + word builder".

C. There are 4 artificial nouns in the sentence.

D. there is a group of nouns represented by double words.

E. In the sentence, there are nouns in 4 places. Correct answer: A, B

Task 4. Read the simple, compound and abstract sentences in the text?

Task 5. Prepare a discussion text based on the information you have heard. Pay attention to the spelling of simple, compound and derived words in the text.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Students are encouraged to develop new ideas and solutions while studying the text. Working on the text stimulates creative thinking and forces students to look for new approaches. This is important for the development of students' creative abilities.

Students gain experience in expressing their thoughts and communicating with others. In the process of working on the text, they have the opportunity to exchange ideas with each other. This process helps to develop their communication skills.

Students develop independent study skills by studying and analyzing text independently. This process encourages them to create their own ideas and expand their knowledge. Independent study skills help students succeed in their lives.

Students develop problem analysis and problem solving skills while studying the text. They will be able to identify the problems presented in the text and offer solutions to them. This process prepares students to solve real-life problems.

CONCLUSION

If each imparted knowledge is proven and explained through such non-traditional visual aids, students' enthusiasm for the subject, the lesson, and the teacher will increase. Repeated use of the same visual aids during several lessons damages the attitude of teachers and students, as well as the quality of the lesson, just as the repetition of words in poetry damages the poetry's artistry. Therefore, according to the requirements of the present time, the student should not only be a discoverer, but also an admirer of this discovery and have a strong will. Only then we, the teachers, can make great progress in raising a mature generation.

References:

1. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). TRUDNOSTI SYNTAKSICHESKOGO ANALYSIS: ZAGADKI INFINITIVA. Academic research in educational sciences, (3).
2. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Brief description of the task of distinguishing word stress in Uzbek and English languages. Innovative scientific research and methods in Uzbekistan, 13-14.

3. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). A concept in cognitive linguistics: the concept of "Tuy" and its universal nature. Innovative scientific research and methods in Uzbekistan, 54-60.
4. Shaikhislamov, N. INTERPRETATION OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. Scientific Progress, 7(1), 59-70.
5. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). In the Field of Modern LinguisticsLinguoculturology. Mirovaya nauka, (8), 33-36.
6. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Scientific-theoretical interpretation of speech in the development of students' copy competencies. Science and Education, 1(5).
7. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Problems of sociolinguistics: status of the language. Science and education in Uzbekistan, 3, 279-281.
8. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Cognitive Linguistics, the Symbolic and Interactive Functions of Language. Obrazovanie i nauka vXXI veke, 1(6), 390-393.
9. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Gender issues in an anthropocentric study of zoonym component metaphors. Obrazovanie i nauka v XXI veke, 1(6), 304-309.
10. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching mother tongue. Issues of science and education in Uzbekistan: problems and solutions, (3), 71-73

